

BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM: ENABLING USER PARTICIPATION IN HOUSING DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION

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1. Introduction

In our information society, industrial production is no longer based on the serial repetition of products designed according to predetermined models or standards. Today, the term ‘mass production’ has been replaced by ‘mass customization’. As Kieran and Timberlake contend: *"Mass production was all about the economy of making things in quantity, but mass customization does not depend on quantity to be cost effective. Mass customization is about cultural production as opposed to the industrial output of mass production."* (Kieran & Timberlake 2004, p.111). The widespread use of Internet can facilitate the participation of customers in the design-production-marketing chain thus enabling mass customization of variety of products, like computers, automobiles, furniture pieces and also houses. Nowadays, through the Internet it is possible to choose a house form a catalogue –for instance, Ikea’s BoKlok (www.boklok.com)–, to customize a room –using, for example, Ikea’s home planner and the 3D Room Planner from Mydeco (mydeco.com/rooms/planner) –, to create tailor-made houses combining diverse materials, colors and textures –as in Kappe and Timberlake’s Living Homes (www.livinghomes.net)– or even to create a plan layout – for example, with Floor Planner (beta.floorplanner.com/demo).

In a near future, tenants and owners could intervene in the design and production process of their homes from remote locations. Some recent research works have strived to create prototype on-line environments that promote user’s participation in housing design. In some of these prototypes, the users facilitate the specifications of their homes by means of multiple choice questionnaires based on texts (Elmasry & Farid 2007) and icons (Huang & Krawczyk 2007). With the information obtained through the questionnaires, the system generates an initial model that suits to the client’s request. Furthermore, a knowledge-based questionnaire has been proposed to enable users to customize prefabricated modular houses describing their needs progressively along the architectural programming stage, thus avoiding having to choose from a collection of finished houses (Huang & Krawczyk 2007).

To further support user’s participation, the dialogue between inhabitant and design system should be extended beyond the initial description of the specifications throughout different stages. As Ruch had observed some thirty years ago, *"...the design process tends to be interdependent, with each subsequent decision depending on the partial layout already developed. Space layout programs which require that all the input information and decisions be provided prior to the beginning of the layout development deny the user the inherent benefits of this interdependent process."* (Ruch 1978, p.152).

Accordingly, in order to ensure the participation of users along a sequence of design stages it would be necessary: 1. to break down the design process in discrete steps and identify those in which the user can intervene and how; 2. to create appropriate interfaces that facilitate a dialogue with a user in a language suited to the knowledge a user has at each stage of the process; and 3. to provide to the user the knowledge needed to assess the final product.

2. BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM: an environment to support the dialogue between system and users

Within the research project BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM, funded by the Spanish National R+D+i Plan 2005-2008, we are developing a participatory system which supports the participation of the different agents –architects, users, manufacturers, builders– in the design and construction process of collective housing using industrialized methods. The purpose of this participation is to combine industrialized building processes with customization in housing design and construction.

The system is the result of the development of a prototype system which enabled the automatic generation of housing units and blocks by means of simple, user-friendly interfaces (Madrazo & Sicilia 2005). This system, however, was stand-alone and limited to a single user, namely, an architect. The newly developed system overcomes this limitation of the prototype, facilitating the participation and interaction of different kinds of user in the process of design and customization of the living units. It is a modular environment which supports the decision-making process in an open and distributed way, allowing inputs from different users at any stage of the process (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Participation of different actors in the system

Housing layouts are based on a parametric grid where cells stand for a type of space (kitchen, bathroom, room). Each cell is represented as a node in a non-directed labeled

graph whose attributes describe a space (privacy, size, and type) while edges indicate the connectivity between spaces and labels specify the degree of visibility and accessibility (wall, door, window, and empty pass).

The generative process uses a non-directed labeled graph to generate the combinations of spaces, and a design constraint list to validate the found solutions. The process is structured in four phases, each one of them with an increasing level of detail, going from dimensionless schemas to scaled floor-plans. At the end of the process, relevant attributes are obtained from the generated layouts in order to facilitate their subsequent search applying backtracking techniques. At the moment of writing, the database contains over 10.000 housing layouts.

Unlike the original prototype system in which housing units were generated in real time, this system works with the concept of centralized pool of solutions. There are two processes that interact with the pool: generate and search. The generative process creates housing units and stores them in the repository for a later use. The search process uses the data gathered in the interfaces (explained below) to retrieve the floor-plans that suit the user's requirements.

The housing layouts that the system generates are distinguished by their flexibility. Rectangular floor-plans can vary in width and height and have multiple layout variations (Figure 2). There is not a housing type for a user type. Rather, each housing unit can be configured in diverse ways in order to better adapt itself to different user's needs.

Figure 2. Housing units generated by BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM

When it comes to search of for a suitable layout, the user is not confronted to a catalogue of complete products whose spatial qualities might not be able to assess from the floor plans. As different studies have shown, the level of understanding of two-dimensional representations of architects and lay people are substantially different (Gobert 1999). Therefore, to let users describe the characteristics of the dwellings it is necessary to employ alternative forms of representation which suit to the skills non-specialists.

2.1 Working spaces

BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM is composed of interwoven working spaces where the different actors can participate in a synchronous and asynchronous manner throughout the whole process of designing, constructing and dwelling in collective housing.

The work spaces and their functionality are as following:

- **PROJECT DEVELOPMENT.** In this working space, developers, architects and building managers specify site properties (area, size), number and type of housing units, building and planning regulations (building volumes and height), and environmental conditions (sound, orientation). Alternative solutions (massing, location) can then be explored for the given site conditions and brief.
- **HOUSING UNIT LAYOUTS.** In this space, architects select a set of units that will be used later in the generation of blocks and towers. The selection becomes a “discovery” process as the architect finds the housing layouts while navigating through the space of solutions which the system has generated in previous project developments. In case that an adequate layout is not found among the existing solutions, the architect can request from the generative system new layouts that conform to the desired criteria (surface, number of rooms, number of bathrooms, open or closed kitchen,...).
- **HOUSING UNIT CONFIGURATION.** Occupants describe their housing program (family members, rooms and their function) by means of user-friendly interfaces that represent housing layouts in a graphic language that can be understood by non-professional users (schematic plans, bubble diagrams, images representing the activities in a space). The system returns the housing units that suit to the criteria defined by occupants. The selected housing units are stored in the system to be used later in the assembly of the block or tower.
- **HOUSING UNITS ASSEMBLY.** In this environment, the architect defines the design criteria for the assembly of living units, for instance: degree of compactness of the block/tower; degree of optimization of building services; minimum distances to access cores (staircases, elevators); material of the structural skeleton (steel, concrete, wood), and so on. Once the design values are set, a generative process produces the solutions that satisfy these criteria.
- **HOUSING UNITS SPECIFICATIONS.** After the housing units have been assembled, there is a process by which occupants and architects collaborate on-line to define the specifications of a living unit (finishing, partitions, and furniture). The building components are retrieved from a XML-based product modeling catalogue, which acts as an interface between building industry (building components suppliers) and the system.
- **BUILDING INFORMATION MODEL.** The information collected through the different work spaces with the participation of the different actors, result in a comprehensive building description which can be exported to an IFC-based model.

In order to interact with the system, it is not necessary to follow the previously outlined working spaces in a linear fashion. Rather, the only prerequisite is to open the “project development” space, where the building development is described (site, number of housing units, type of occupant) and users are registered. All other spaces can be activated at any moment during the project lifecycle.

In this paper, we will focus on the processes that are part of the HOUSING UNIT CONFIGURATION working space, whose goal is to obtain from the user the data that the system needs to generate and/or search housing designs.

3. HOUSING UNIT CONFIGURATION WORKSPACE

If we want users to participate in a system that will assist them in customizing their homes then the interfaces must be suitable to them. User interfaces should be usable and easy to learn and they should be based on a language that conforms to the knowledge of the user. Furthermore, they need to guide and inform the user through the interaction process. Interfaces should enable users to understand their choices by being aware of the implications of these. Also, they should contain metaphors and analogies that lead to the association of ideas. For all of these purposes, it is important to use adequate terms, icons, images, colors and highlighting techniques which altogether give rise to a language suited to the user's abilities. Finally, the interaction should be structured as a sequence encompassing a minimum number of steps. (Dillon 2003, pp. 453-458)

To facilitate the dialogue between user and system, we have created a sequence of interfaces that allow a lay person who is not aware of the rules governing the generation of layouts and does not understand necessarily architectural graphic conventions interact with the system. The Housing Unit Configuration workspace consists of a sequence of four interfaces (Figure 3):

1. Occupants and spaces
2. Spatial qualities
3. Room interrelation
4. Plan layout

Figure 3. Dialogue space between system and user

The sequence is structured in such a way that the information acquired in one interface becomes an input for the next. Following the information collected from different users, a process of generation of the block or tower is prompted to assemble the housing units in a block or tower. Then, after each housing unit has its place in the block, a 3d model

of the interior housing unit allows each user to determine the finishes and partitions in a dialogue with the architect.

In the next sections, we will describe the characteristics of each one of the dialogues of the sequence.

3.1 INTERFACE 1: Occupants and spaces

Figure 4. Interface to define spaces and occupants

In the first interface of the Housing Unit Configuration process (Figure 4), the future owner/s or tenant/s describe the basic characteristics –such as total surface, number of rooms– of the dwelling that suit to their needs and lifestyle. We have assumed that the user might be a person (or group) with no previous knowledge of architectural conventions.

With this interface, the user describes the family structure (single person, couple, couples with children,) by selecting its members represented as icons. The selected members appear inside a rectangle which represents the total surface of the dwelling. This way, the identity between family unit and housing unit is visualized: all family members appear inside the space they share, the dwelling. The rectangle represents the limits of this shelter, the enclosure where domestic life takes place, where family members and their possessions are protected.

As the value of the surface changes in a slider, the size of the rectangle varies accordingly. The range of surface values in the slider is related to the number of inhabitants. To adjust both, surface and inhabitants, it is possible to fix the surface and modify the number of inhabitants, or vice versa.

Once the user has selected the surface value and number of occupants, a schematic layout is generated and displayed. The default configuration –number of rooms, number of bathrooms and number of exterior spaces– can be interactively modified by means of three sliders located at the bottom of the plan. The range of values of the sliders is

related to the surface and number of inhabitants previously chosen. A 60 sqm. flat, for instance, can have up to three rooms according to the constraints built in the system.

The plan layout is represented in the simplest possible form, as a rectangular area partitioned into smaller rectangles which stand for the rooms. The plan is a-dimensional and the size of a room does not reflect its actual surface. This is the kind of representation of a spatial layout that a lay person is likely to draw. In this regard, this schematic plan is intended to be a kind of cognitive map, that is to say, a visual representation of the experience that a person has of the space of a house.

Besides depicting the spatial organization in a way that is recognizable by a non-expert user, it is necessary to describe the functions of the different rooms. As Juhani Pallasmaa pointed out, "*The phenomenology of architecture is founded on verbs rather than nouns.*" (Pallasmaa 1994). This is proved by the fact that spaces are usually named after the activities we carry on them. As George Perec has argued in his book *Espèces d'espaces* (1974), it is almost impossible to imagine a room without a function. A room can also be named after the object that identifies its function like, for example, a bedroom. In this regard, David Canter maintains that "...*furnishings may be regarded as 'markers' arranged around the house to indicate the type of place an occupant wants any part of the house to be.*" (Canter 1977). Other rooms, however, are strongly associated with specific activities, like cooking in a kitchen. Still, there are rooms which cannot be described by a specific function or activity which –paradoxically– we call "living rooms".

Typically, a person has a preconceived idea of the spaces of a house and the functions associated to them (e.g. eating in the kitchen, sleeping in the bedroom). With this interface, we help the user to overcome such preconceptions by asking for the activities to carry out in each room. In this way, the future occupant realizes that a living room could also be a place to sleep, to eat, to study, to exercise, to play an instrument or to work. The user specifies which activities will take place in a room by selecting between one to four activities from a predefined list. The suggested activities –to exercise, to sleep or rest, to play, to study, to work, to watch TV, to play instruments, to talk, to get ready or dressed, to party, to iron the cloth, to hang the cloth, to take care of the children, to listen music and to read– can be performed in any room displayed in the layout.

3.2 INTERFACE 2: Spatial qualities

Figure 5. Interface to define spatial qualities

Once the user has provided information about family structure, spatial layout and activities to carry in the rooms, in the next interface the characteristics of each room (e.g. the level of privacy, the size of the room, the number of openings) are determined by means of photographs displaying people performing different activities inside a room (Figure 5).

As the user goes through a list displaying the different rooms previously chosen, photographs of the activities that can take place at each selected room are displayed. The photographs which are shown correspond to the previous selection of activities. For instance, if the user had associated the activities “watching TV”, “reading”, “partying” to the living room in the previous interface, then images of people performing those activities are now shown.

The images have been carefully selected to reflect contemporary lifestyles, showing different activities taking place in diverse places (e.g. working with a laptop in a living room, exercising in front of the TV). The users are expected to identify themselves with the images, selecting those that better represent the atmosphere of the room they have in mind. Each image is associated to a series of attributes, which describe the spatial qualities of the depicted place: large or small room, with small or big openings, lit or dark, private or public. The relation between images and spatial qualities has been previously described in the system (Figure 6).

PICTURE	SPACE	ACTIVITIES	FAMILY STRUCTURE	AGE	NUMBER OF PEOPLE	SURFACE SIZE	OPENINGS
	living room	watching TV	couples	young	7	big	windows
	dining room	talking	roommates				doors
	kitchen	eating					
		partying					

Figure 6. Table of images with associated attributes

By selecting images, the user provides information of the spatial attributes of the different rooms. As Najjar contends, “*Pictures also seem to be better than text or auditory instructions for communicating spatial information.*” (Najjar 1998). From all images displayed of the activities associated to the selected room, up to three might be selected. Upon selecting an image, a short description of its spatial qualities appears at the lower bottom.

In his book *The Psychology of Place*, Canter argued that “*There is clear evidence that visual representations of places capture much which is psychologically significant about them.*” (Canter 1977, p.176). Individuals could feel more closely related to a picture than to a verbal or textual description because they see themselves reflected in the image. Photographic images are used in publicity for the same reasons. Individuals who feel familiar with an image, or recognize in it a lifestyle they would like to adhere, are also attracted to consume the products on display. Also, photographs help to recall a place experienced in the past or to imagine a new one which the image evokes.

As Gaston Bachelard affirms in his book *La Poétique de l'espace* (1957) images can move people deeply with all its psychological resilience, charged with memory and imagination. Through the photographs displayed in the interface, users can gain a sense of place by visualizing the ambience of their future home, projecting their memories onto the images.

3.3 INTERFACE 3: Room interrelation

Figure 7. Interface to define room locations

In the third interface (Figure 7), a housing unit is represented as a bubble diagram made up of three concentric circles: the inner one representing spaces which are not in contact with the façade; the outer one, spaces which are within the façade, like balconies; and the intermediate one, for spaces which lie in-between inside and outside, like closed galleries and the like. Over these three circles, smaller circles representing rooms are placed. The diagram is a-dimensional although the proportion of room sizes is preserved.

At the outset, the placement and size of the rooms in the diagram is based on the information gathered in the two previous phases. For instance, if the user had selected more than one photograph of a living room with a balcony, then the bubble diagram will show the circle “living room” next to the balcony area. Similarly, if more than one picture of a small room was selected then one of the circles representing the room will be a small one.

Whereas the schematic plan of the first interface was based on the subdivision of a rectangular area in smaller rooms, this diagram is based on the aggregation of interrelated rooms. Space is thought of as expanding from the center towards a periphery. Rooms placed on the edge of the large circle are closer to the light, and those placed near the center further away from it. This way, the diagram stresses the activities taking place in each space as well as the quality of spaces in terms of day lighting. With this diagrammatic representation of a plan layout, the user is induced to reflect on the relationship between the quality of the spaces and its position within the whole, and their hierarchy with regard to the activities that will take place in them.

As Paul Laseau has contended, diagramming in architecture is a language consisting of both “*a vocabulary and a grammar, but in graphic form*” (Laseau 2000, p.123). The representation of the layout as a bubble diagram encompasses a language with which the user can communicate with the system: the vocabulary consists of circles representing rooms, whereas the actions (dragging, joining, separating) performed over the circles constitute the grammar. By interacting with the diagram, the user provides to the system the information to position rooms and their interrelationship. For instance, if the user wants to have a bathroom with natural ventilation would move the circle “bathroom” next to the façade. Similarly, if a bathroom directly connected to a bedroom is desired, it is enough to put the two circles, representing bedroom and bathroom, together. Also, two separated rooms –for instance, a living room and a kitchen– can be joined to make a larger room.

3.4 INTERFACE 4: Plan Layout

Figure 8. Interface displaying plan layouts

From all the data gathered in the previous interfaces, the application performs a query to the system to obtain the ten floor-plans that better fit to the user's requirements. Floor plans are retrieved from the repository to be displayed schematically (Figure 8). Out of the ten layouts, the user can choose up to three which will be used in the subsequent customization process, once the block or tower is generated.

As Laseau explains "...a plan can provide a heightened sense of the qualities of spaces while retaining a comprehensive view and a strong sense of orientation." (Laseau 2000, p.37). To emphasize these qualities of the floor plan, connections between colored spaces are depicted by means of arrows so that the user can get a quick understanding of the circulation pattern which starts at the home entrance.

This schematic plan epitomizes one more step in the learning process of the user interacting with the system. This synthetic representation brings together the previous diagrammatic representations and the plans drawn according to architectural conventions. In doing so, all the information collected from the previous interfaces is represented in a simplified architectural scaled plan omitting those graphic conventions that a lay person can find difficult to understand.

With this interface, the user can verify whether the requisites described in the course of the previous dialogues have been incorporated in the floor plans. For instance, after selecting "attribute" in the menu, each spatial characteristic is shown on the corresponding room. If "access" is chosen, then connections between rooms are shown as arrows.

3.5. INTERFACE 5: Interior space

Figure 9. Interface to navigate in the interior of the housing unit

Once the process of describing user's requirements is completed with the previous interfaces, the next interface displays the interior of the dwellings in order to select building components (types of door and window; kitchen configuration), finishes and materials in collaboration with the architect (Figure 9). Before this interaction is possible, housing units selected by users have been inserted in a block or tower

generated in the HOUSING UNITS ASSEMBLY working space. Also, the building components have been previously stored in a catalogue created for the system which manufacturers can use to describe their products.

In principle, with three-dimensional walkthroughs it seems possible to overcome some of the difficulties that lay people encounter to understand a floor plan: spaces can be “seen” as they are “in reality”, and movements from one room to the next can be simulated. Still, one more step further in this progression from abstract to realistic representations would lead to the use of immersive virtual environments to design homes (Kitchens & Shiratuddin 2007).

The purpose of the 3d model we have created for this interface is not just to visualize and navigate through the interior space of a living unit but mostly to change some of its components (partitions, doors and windows) interactively, with the participation of different users (occupants, architects) in Internet. To meet these requirements, it has been necessary to create an interactive graphic engine especially for the system.

The 3-d model is created from the geometric information encoded in the housing layout created by the generator. The visualization in three dimensions –surfaces, lighting, and motion– is done through an interactive graphic engine specially created for the system. The graphic engine uses dynamic light maps to represent different light conditions depending on the time of day in order to provide a convincing depiction of the interior space.

At the end of the interaction, the components selected in the 3d model become part of a complete building description with which begins the process of design and optimization of the block or tower made up of the customized dwellings.

4. Technical implementation

To develop these interfaces it was necessary to use technologies that supported the communication between the different components of the system (generator and search engines) by means of a set of compatible and usable interfaces. The system implementation has been done with Microsoft .Net technologies, including C# and WPF/XAML, along with the markup language XML for data file exchange. The graphic interfaces has been created with Expression Blend, a tool provided by the Microsoft Platform with a widget to support the graphical subsystem WPF and hardware acceleration via DirectX (Figure 10).

Figure 10. System components

5. Conclusions and future work

The work we have developed so far needs to be considered as part of a prototype system which would need further development in order to achieve fully interactive interfaces that would support, guide and educate the user along the customization process. Further work is necessary to improve the design of the interfaces and, particularly, to enhance the dialogue between user and system so that the interacting process becomes a truly learning experience for the user. In order to properly assess the work achieved with the interfaces here described, it must also be taken into account that they are only a part of a far more comprehensive system which includes other working environments, including those to generate housing units and blocks or towers.

6. Acknowledgements

The research project BARCODE HOUSING SYSTEM with the reference number BIA2005-08707-C02-01 has been funded by the Spanish National R+D+i plan 2005-2008. Angel Martin Cojo, architect, has participated in the design of the architectural system, and Mar González, technical engineer in computer science, has implemented the generative system of the housing units. The programming and implementation of the interfaces described in this paper have been done by Gonçal Costa, technical engineer in multimedia.

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